

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PARENT AND CHILD AS A FACTOR IN THE FORMATION OF THE ADJECTIVAL HULK DURING ADOLESCENCE

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the influence of the relationship between parents and their adolescent children on the formation of addictive behavior, the importance of an integrated approach in studying the problem of addictive behavior.*

Keywords: *family, parental relationships, addictive behavior, verprotection, control severity, incomplete family.*

The main link in child socialization is the family. The patterns of behavior established in the family help to adequately perceive the integrity of the adolescent personality, himself and others. It is worth noting that the study of the condition of a teenager prone to addictive behavior in a family environment provided for a complex task for a psychologist, that is, to correct not only adolescent behavior, but also the behavior of his parents. It is in this system of family interactions that the interpersonal relationships of the parent with the child are implied. "Addictive behavior", called subordinate behavior Ham, is a disorder of behavior that occurs through the improper use of things that change a person's mental state. In this, mental and physical dependence occurs. Experience shows that often a practicing psychologist pays little attention to the fact that it is a teenager with addictive behavior who knows closely with family members. Even so, he will want to delve into the disorders in family interactions. As a result of this, firstly, situations arise in interactions with the family that do not appeal to both parties, offending each other; secondly, the methods of purposeful psychocorrection remain unworkable. Therefore, at the stage of making psychodiagnostics, it is necessary to create a basis for effective communication. In halting this problem, in a certain sense, E.G. Eidemiller V.V. The OMTQ ("analysis of family relationships") methodology developed by the justicians can also help. The questionnaire consists of scales that help to identify certain retreats in the relationships that parents and parents establish with their children. These scales indicate, for example, tightness of control over a teenager (g+), lack of control (g -), constant satisfaction of adolescent needs (u+) or absolute non-satisfaction (u -), abundance and complexity of requirements for a teenager (T+) or lack of such exactingness (T -), an abundance of pre-adolescent bans (Z+), or non-availability of it (Z -), a sharpness of punishment for a teenager (S+) or its opposite (S -) if the requirements are not met. The survey consisted of opinions regarding the upbringing of a specific child, and each opinion was numbered in order, it was these ordinal numbers that were also recorded in the "answer letterhead".

The above methodology was precisely the one that helped to identify disorders in family relationships in which an adolescent with an addictive hookah lives and was tried in families of different categories. A survey of 240 families found a number of patterns. For example, the imposition of high adult requirements on the child has been found to cause various complications at different stages of the child's development. The fact that a parent demands more from their teenage child has not actually found evidence, since the suitability rate for a young school-age

child compared to a teenager is actually lower. At the same time, the control of the behavior of a teenager gave high indicators. Only in rare cases does the father or mother not interfere in the affairs of the teenager, considering him an adult. Another thing is clearly defined that adults want to see childhood qualities in adolescents rather than adult qualities. In practice, it was found that one in two parents and one in a mother admitted that from a small school age they had a lack of confidence in the upbringing of their child. Because especially young family representatives are always in doubt about the decisions made regarding the upbringing of children, whether the plans are correct or not. Ultimately, they cause situations of fear of something, helplessness, helplessness, difficulty even in ordinary situations. In this and other similar difficulties, scientists believe, there is also a role for external factors: for example, it is natural that psychogenic factors also play an influential role in the way in which such things as "thinking", "attitudes", "traditions" are derived from the previous family of a father or mother. Therefore, it is necessary to identify similar aspects in the father and mother and carry out targeted corrective work on this basis. In the case of eliminating disorders in relationships identified in the family, however, it is desirable to use in psychology the appropriate means of self-justifying mechanisms, namely: influence, imitation, identification, referentiality. If the disorders in the relationship were deeply veined, showing their impact on all areas of family life, then it will be necessary to look for radical, strict measures. We decided to study the character of their relationship with children of the same age between 50 mothers with a teenage son and a daughter. In order to ensure data objectivity and validity, we worked with 25 full-family representatives who actively participated in the previous studies, as well as women with so many non-family representatives. Our goal was to identify the withdrawal, conflicts and their root causes in the relationship between mother and child, based on the characteristics of adolescence. We are quoted in the above content in the study E.G. Eidemiller V.V. We used the OMTQ ("analysis of family relations") methodology developed by the justicians.

First of all, it is worth noting that mothers, no matter what family vacancy, realize that control over the behavior of a teenage child, being especially attentive to them. On the answers to the questions, we were convinced that, especially in the answers to the soldiers of mothers in a full family, the criterion "tightness of control over a teenager" received an indicator of 3.6 in conditions where the maximum indicator was calculated 7, that is, the application of rigidity to girls in the first place is an important criterion of upbringing. At the same time, the difference was evident in the opinions of full-family mothers raising a girl and a boy, since in the response of 85.7% of mothers raising a girl, only 14.3% of those with a son, the opinion of the condition for control over a teenager was outlined. In a similar case, the lack of control over adolescents showed 25 and 37.5 percent, respectively, that is, from the answers of mothers who have a boy, it turned out that they lack control over the teenager ($g+ - 37.5\%$). The differences in the problems of raising a similar girl and a boy were also visible in the face of other poses. For example, in a case where the ever-fulfilling needs of a teenage girl were almost 100 percent according to mothers, the full satisfaction of the needs of a boy was determined in one of every three answers ($u+ - 33\%$); even in the full satisfaction of the requirements for a teenager, there are gender differences in the opinion of their parents (25% and 50%, respectively); The reasons for such a condition were attributed to the fact that the mother in other positions was associated with problems in herself. Because mothers of 75 percent of girls and mothers of only 50 percent of boys are afraid of losing their child (Fu), and mothers of 43 percent of girls and mothers of all sons are known to have little developed maternal

qualities in their answers (NRCH), predisposition to give birth to a child (14.3 and 28.6, respectively), mood sensitivity in different situations, lack of competence in Having psychologically analyzed the questionnaire, it also became known that in some issues mothers are in almost the same pose, regardless of the gender of the child. For example, it has been difficult to find differences in both groups, such as the abundance and complexity of adolescent pretensions (T+), the abundance of adolescent pretensions (Z+), the absence of adolescent pretensions (Z -) in certain responses, the tendency to punish the adolescent, and his or her severity (s+), or softness (s -), the tendency to emphasize masculine qualities (PMK). From these, the general conclusion was that after the child reaches adolescence, most mothers begin to make mistakes anyway, depending on the situation, but in their opinion, it is necessary to stand firm on a child of this age, it is imperative to control him, and if the child is mistaken, it is also the responsibility of the parents to punish him. In general, regardless of the sex of the child, his behavior is obliged to be in the control of adults. Continuing to analyze the answers in coefficients, paying attention to the type of family, showed that in the opinions of mothers of a complete and dysfunctional family there was no sharp difference in tension or severity in relation to the behavior of the child (3,6 and 3,3). Anyway, it turned out that strict mothers in relation to a boy are more often among representatives of a dysfunctional family (3,2 and 2,5 in a full family). So, in our conditions, the severity towards girls is higher, and the lack of severity in a dysfunctional family in boys turned out to be higher than in all groups (3,1). In relation to girls, on the contrary, there was a more pronounced manifestation of control over girls in a dysfunctional family. Now we compare these indicators with other educational criteria. It is their duty that the father and mother regularly meet the various material and spiritual needs of their children. Among the recommended questions, we focused on the answers that fall under the criterion of "always satisfying adolescent needs." Most mothers who are raising a girl in a full family have noted to their daughters that they are always ready to buy what they want, in which the cost of the thing is also not so significant, they spare nothing from the girl. In this sense, this positivity is more acute in those who have a teenage boy brought up in a dysfunctional family, only one in four of them has such an attitude towards their son, in their opinion, it is not necessary to do what the child says, moreover, to teach him something, explain to him is difficult, household chores are no exception, so the mother Such an approach is characteristic of two categorical family representatives. The above circumstances were also reflected in a certain sense in the answers to questions that fall under the criterion of "the abundance and complexity of requirements for a teenager" of the questionnaire. For example, almost all mothers, regardless of the sex of the child, want to put different tasks in front of him, help them in household chores, especially those who are raising a girl in a full family and raising a son in a dysfunctional family (3,0 and 2,9). Because regardless of the gender of the child in his teens, it was noted that if he had a younger brother (sister) than him, he would certainly look after them, sometimes they were forced to look after his brother. Therefore, it turned out that all indicators are higher than the middle. Only most mothers in a dysfunctional family have noted that their requirements for their daughters are gentle (0,5), it is impossible to be so demanding. And some data are contradictory in the answers of mothers in a full family: in conditions where those who said that it is necessary to be demanding were only 70 percent, there were also those who claimed 100 percent that there was no such pose. This is also a complication in upbringing, and it is precisely such an ambivalent pose that can lead to a breakdown in relationships. Thus, the survey we conducted also showed the presence of certain problems in the interaction of parents with their

teenage children, precisely because these are the reasons for the deterioration of the relationship between the mother and the teenage child. The most common of such reasons in our "baby" environment is first of all the fear of losing a child (Fu), that is, the fear of losing his affection, because in reality women are premature mothers in many cases, and when their child steps on the threshold of adolescence, they still have not very developed parental qualities (NRCH), therefore the presence of doubt of the mother berylinguism, the lack of competency (competence) in upbringing (VK), therefore, the existing shortcomings in oneself were noted, such as a tendency to give birth to a child (PNA). All these are psychological factors, which in the relationship of the mother with the child are not really so understood by the mother. This thing is characteristic of mothers of a dysfunctional family, in which the desire to raise their child as well as in their dreams and imaginations also arises from the extreme strength. From mutual conversations, it turned out that since a woman in a dysfunctional family often lives with her own father and mother, often adults from them, they also have control over a teenager, the reason is that they realize that in upbringing problems there is a share not only of herself, but also of them. When the problem is appears, he seeks the blame not from himself, but from the adults next to him. This is also an ethnopsychological identity in US, and a woman who has lost her husband is not alone in most cases, but with loved ones. In some cases, the child is completely transferred to adult education, he himself goes to another fast. Of course, when raising a teenage child in a full and dysfunctional family, absolute differences are not felt, such as paying attention to his gender. Because in both cases it turned out that there is special attention to raising a girl child. Because it is from this period that the preparation of a teenage girl in an Uzbek family for family life, for marriage begins. That is why everyone pays special attention to their upbringing. In the case of a non-family, it is known that mothers have more hope than there is a boy, because of the attention they receive, the control over their behavior is stricter. But our mothers try to associate more in the problems of raising a boy with errors arising from their gender. Therefore, even more misunderstandings in upbringing became evident in mothers in a full and dysfunctional family who have a son. But while there is no clear difference in the emphasis on the masculine qualities of a single-parent with a mother raising a son together with her father, it turned out that mothers of a dysfunctional family are more attentive in controlling the behavior of a child, seeing his shortcomings. It is they who are also much more democratic in punishing the child. It is worth noting that the study of the state of a teenager in a family environment provided for a complex task for a psychologist, that is, to correct not only adolescent behavior, but also the behavior of his parents. It is in this system of family interactions that the interpersonal relationships of the parent with the child are implied.

Experience shows that often a practicing psychologist pays little attention to precisely his close acquaintance with the family. Even so, he will want to delve into the disorders in family interactions. As a result of this, firstly, situations arise in interactions with the family that do not appeal to both parties, offending each other; secondly, the methods of purposeful psychocorrection remain unworkable. Therefore, at the stage of making psychodiagnostics, it is necessary to create a basis for effective communication. In place of the conclusion, it can be said that in the system of family relations, disorders in the above-mentioned factors lead to the formation of addictive behavior in a teenager. The process of raising a child in families with spiritual harmony with a teenager, trust, mutual understanding, a desire to solve complex issues without conflicts, respect for the personality of a teenager is successful.

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